

Supplementary Fig. S3 Doubled haploid plants derived from CDC Stanley x CDC Landmark determined as **normal** based on **digital karyotyping (left)**; Each panel shows the genomic position of a given chromosome in 1Mb bins on the physical map of the CDC Landmark reference genome in the x-axis with points showing the normalized number of reads mapping to the respective bin. The vertical axis shows both normalized read count (left) and chromosome dosage (right). The parental allele for individual SNP variants is shown on top for CDC Landmark (red) and CDC Stanley (blue) alleles. Centromere positions are showing as black triangle, and **FISH (right)**; Sites of hybridization are shown with fluorescence-labelled probes, GAAn (green) and pAs1 (red). The chromosomes were identified according to the standard FISH karyotype (Danilova et al. 2012)

StanleyLandmarkDH01021-0-2

Normal: 42 chromosomes

StanleyLandmarkDH01029-0-3

Normal: 42 chromosomes

StanleyLandmarkDH01031-0-1

Normal: 42 chromosomes

StanleyLandmarkDH01031-0-3

Normal: 42 chromosomes

StanleyLandmarkDH01052-0-8

Normal: 42 chromosomes

StanleyLandmarkDH01053-0-1

Normal: 42 chromosomes

StanleyLandmarkDH01072-0-3

Normal: 42 chromosomes

StanleyLandmarkDH01108-0-2

Normal: 42 chromosomes

StanleyLandmarkDH01108-0-3

Normal: 42 chromosomes

StanleyLandmarkDH02008-0-1

Normal: 42 chromosomes

StanleyLandmarkDH02017-0-2

Normal: 42 chromosomes

Supplementary Fig. S3 DH plants derived from CDC Stanley x CDC Landmark determined as **abnormal** based on **digital karyotyping (left)**. Each panel shows the genomic position of a given chromosome in 1Mb bins on the physical map of the CDC Landmark reference genome in the x-axis with points showing the normalized number of reads mapping to the respective bin. The vertical axis shows both normalized read count (left) and chromosome dosage (right). The parental allele for individual SNP variants is shown on top for CDC Landmark (red) and CDC Stanley (blue) alleles. Centromere positions are showing as black triangle. and, **FISH (right)**

StanleyLandmarkDH02074-1

Chr no	AA	BB	DD
1	2	2	2
2	2	2	2
3	2	2	2
4	2	2	2
5	2	2	2
6	2	2	2
7	1	2	2

- Total chromosomes: 41 + 1 centric fragment (arrow)
- Single copy of 7A

StanleyLandmarkDH02074-3

Copy number

Chr no	AA	BB	DD
1	2	2	2
2	2	2	2
3	2	2	2
4	2	2	2
5	2	2	2
6	2	2	2
7	1*	2	2

- Total chromosomes: 41
- Single copy of 7A

StanleyLandmarkDH01018-0-4

Chr no	AA	BB	DD
1	2	2	2
2	2	2	2
3	2	2	1+1*
4	2	2	2
5	2	2	2
6	2	2	2
7	2	2	2

- Total chromosomes: 42
- Hetero deletion of 3DL (1/2)* arrow
- 3B: homozygous for a deletion

StanleyLandmarkDH02014-0-2

Chr no	AA	BB	DD
1	2	2	2
2	2	0	3*
3	2	2	2
4	2	2	2
5	2	2	2
6	3*	2	1*
7	2	2	2

- Total chromosomes: 41
- Zero copy of 2B
- Three copies of 2D*
- Three copies of 6A*
- One copy of 6D*

StanleyLandmarkDH02014-0-3

Chr no	AA	BB	DD
1	2	2	2
2	2	0	4*
3	2	2	2
4	2	2	2
5	2	2	2
6	2	2	2
7	2	2	2

- Total chromosomes: 42
- Four copies of 2D*
- Zero copy of 2B

StanleyLandmarkDH02014-0-4

Chr no	AA	BB	DD
1	2	2	2
2	2	1	3*
3	2	2	2
4	2	2	2
5	2	2	2
6	3*	2	1
7	2	2	2

- Total chromosomes: 42
- One copy of 2B
- Three copies of 2D*
- Three copies of 6A*
- One copy of 6D*

StanleyLandmarkDH02014-0-7

Chr no	AA	BB	DD
1	2	2	2
2	2	0	4*
3	2	2	2
4	2	2	2
5	2	2	2
6	4*	2	0
7	2	2	2

- Total chromosomes: 42
- Zero copy of 2B
- Four copies of 2D*
- Four copies of 6A*
- Zero copy of 6D*

StanleyLandmarkDH02014-0-8

Copy number

Chr no	AA	BB	DD
1	2	2	2
2	2	1*	3*
3	2	2	2
4	2	2	2
5	2	2	2
6	3*	2	1*
7	2	2	2

- Total chromosomes: 42
- One copy of 2B
- Three copies of 2D*
- Three copies of 6A*
- One copy of 6D*

StanleyLandmarkDH02017-0-8

Chr no	AA	BB	DD
1	2	2	2
2	2	2	3*
3	2	2	2
4	2	2	2
5	2	2	2
6	4*	2	0
7	2	2	2

- Total chromosomes: 43
- Three copies of 2D*
- Four copies of 6A*
- Zero copy of 6D*

StanleyLandmarkDH01003-0-1

Chr no	AA	BB	DD
1	2	2	2
2	2	2	2*
3	2	2	2
4	2	2	2
5	2	2	2
6	2	2	2
7	2	2	2

- Total chromosomes: 44
- Homozygous deletion of 2DS (1/3)* (large arrows)
- Two copies of telo 2DS (arrows)

StanleyLandmarkDH01003-0-3

Chr no	AA	BB	DD
1	2	2	2
2	2	2	2*
3	2	2	2
4	2	2	2
5	2	2	2
6	2	2	2
7	2	2	2

- Total chromosomes: 43
- Homozygous deletion of 2DS (1/3)* (large arrows)
- One copy of telo 2DS (arrows)

StanleyLandmarkDH02074-2

Chr no	AA	BB	DD
1	2	2	2
2	2	2	2
3	2	2	2
4	2	2	2
5	2	2	2
6	2	2	2
7	2*	2	2

- Total chromosomes: 42
- Homo terminal deletion of Chromosome 7A*